

FORMATION OF WRITING, READING SKILLS IN CHILDREN OF OLDER PRESCHOOL AGE

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Abstract. This article the tasks of the preparatory period of literacy training are scheduled for September, October. During this period, the following works are carried out.

Keyword: language as speech, education, method, educator, science.

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ НАВЫКОВ ПИСЬМА, ЧТЕНИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ СТАРШЕГО ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА.

Аннотация. В данной статье задачи подготовительного периода обучения грамоте намечены на сентябрь, октябрь. За это время были выполнены следующие работы

Ключевые слова: язык как речь, образование, метод, педагог, наука.

In literacy training, literacy training is separated into two periods. The preparatory period is the main period (preparation for Literacy).

The tasks of the preparatory period for teaching literacy are planned in September, October. During this period, the following works are carried out: correctly pronouncing sounds and identifying and forming the word's perceptions of the sound composition to give an understanding of vowel and consonant sounds. Development of phonemic perception and imagination based on teaching to distinguish between resonant and non-resonant sounds development of simple analysis and synthesis skills:

- (a) division of a sentence into words, division of words into syllables;
- b) determining the position of certain sounds (at the beginning, between and at the end of the word);
- C) determination of the sequence and number of sounds in a word;
- g) teaching to make syllables, words from sounds;
- d) teaching to distinguish sounds in hearing;

In the preparatory group, the following works are carried out during the 2nd Stage - main period (October - may) of the section on teaching literacy of the direction of speech, reading and preparation for literacy:

Introducing a given sound with a letter symbol. Teaching to perform exercises on sound-letter analysis and synthesis using cross-letters; syllable reading;

To compose syllables and words using cross-syllables and to teach them to read them in syllables. In preparedness, the results should be appropriate for the age of children and carried in sequence. In the development of training, the goals and objectives of the subject, the expected results, the necessary equipment, the course of the training are fully covered. The topics of training should be understandable to children, practical work and various interactive games suitable for the age of children, interesting and varied. During classes, children perform finger exercises in refreshing moments, special games with letters, (picking, picking), perform practical tasks, learn the alphabet, and the skills of being able to read the joints are strengthened. At the end of each session, questions were asked to determine and consolidate the knowledge of the children. From the early days when Uzbekistan gained its independence, it entered the path of building a new, developed society. With its dedicated work and peaceful life, our hardworking ring began to carry out deep reforms in all areas in order to take a strong place among the world's progressive countries. All the historical changes and updates carried out on the establishment of a great future state have a tremendous impact on the hearts and minds of our compatriots.

- education is decisive in the development of speech of preschool children, especially in the conditions of a modern unfavorable speech environment;

- teaching speech is a creative process in which hard molds such as " ...to ... " do not coincide and are determined by the age laws of speech development and the individual characteristics of the child;

- on the basis of speech development, there should be a communicative approach, in particular: mastering the native language should be added to the activities of speech communication, educational conditions should be brought closer to the conditions of natural communication;

- the nature of the interaction of an adult with a child in a teaching situation should be determined by the form of communication that is the;

- speech teaching should be based on independent language learning activities of children and related to other types of child activity. Currently, the development of the problem of teaching speech to preschool children is carried out based on these methodological developments. The main reason why children of preschool age cannot express their opinion clearly and fluently enough is that:

- 1) elimination of defects in children's speech;
- 2) development of the speech culture of educators and educators;

3) grow oral and written speech by working on vocabulary, vocabulary, sentence;

4) when working on linkage speech, methods of using games and exercises, training have not been developed. Children successfully master the sounds of their native language with the help of an educator who speaks clearly and intelligibly, pronounces phrases, words and each sound separately, that is, has good diction. Often, the pronunciation of educators is somewhat ambiguous and incomprehensible, they pronounce sounds and words without sufficiently opening the mouth, some sounds are swallowed, consonants are pronounced inexplicably. The educator must comply with the literary standards of pronunciation, eliminate the influence of various dialects, local dialects in his speech, correctly put emphasis on words.

THE ANTONYM WORDS GAME

This is a game of watchdog groups. We hope that play training will help the development of children's logical thinking. Gamindividual, groupbilanhowever. 'yinshartiqo: Nurtureribolagabirsuzniaytadi, child shusuşnigaramaşnanglatiçinitopadi. Today, such a demand for speech is imposed on the consciousness and thinking of a person in order to know his native language well and learn a second language efficiently. For the first time, the implementation of such requirements begins with preschool institutions. When teaching Russian-speaking children to the Uzbek language, it is necessary to know the correct pronunciation criteria for them; to rely on the pronunciation of each word when performing exercises should be the main goal of all training. Every vowel, syllable, vowel consonants and word in the Uzbek language must be able to pronounce correctly. The language of each people is measured by the riches in his speech. Great allomas also looked at the enrichment of the language, which is the weapon of interaction between people, with great attention and respect for its tone and pronunciation rules

REFERENCES

1. Abdullayeva N. R. et al. Study of Alkylphenol-Formaldehyde Oligomers Modified with Amines Containing Imidazoline Fragments as Corrosion Inhibitors in the Composition of Preservation Fluids.
2. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:gXdc-Kbh4SoJ:scholar.google.com/>
3. Abdullayeva, Nigora, and Sevinch Bahodir qizi Bahodirova. "TALABALARNING KASBIY KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *ILM FAN TARAQQIYOTIDA ZAMONAVIY METODLARNING QO'LLANILISHI* 3.5 (2023): 11-14.
4. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:6DP5L0_O4sgJ:scholar.google.com/

5. Abdullayeva, N. R. (2018). Nitrogen-containing organic compounds as inhibitors of corrosion in an aqueous medium. *Processes of Petrochemistry and Oil Refining*, (3), 282-294.
6. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=DEaSb2sAAA&AJ&citation_for_view=DEaSb2sAAAAJ:LkGwnXOMwfcC
7. Abdullayeva N. R. MONOALKYL (C8-C12) PHENOLFORMALDEHYDE OLIGOMERS MODIFIED BY IMIDAZOLINES ON THE BASIS OF FATTY ACIDS OF THE VEGETABLE OILS AS A COMPONENT OF THE CONSERVATION LIQUIDS. – 2019.
8. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=DEaSb2sAAA&AJ&citation_for_view=DEaSb2sAAAAJ:_FxGoFyzp5QC
9. Abdullayeva, N. R., Amiraslanova, M. N., Aliyeva, L. I., Akhmedbekova, S. F., & Rustamov, R. A. (2019). SYNTHESIS AND MODIFICATION OF ALKYL PHENOL-FORMALDEHYDE OLIGOMERS WITH IMIDAZOLINES ON THE BASES OF FATTY ACIDS OF VEGETABLE ORIGIN. *Processes of petrochemistry and oil refining*, 20(1), 25-32.
10. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=DEaSb2sAAA&AJ&citation_for_view=DEaSb2sAAAAJ:_kc_bZDykSQC
11. Abdullayeva, Narmina R., et al. "Imidazolines on the bases of fatty acids of palm oil as modifiers of phenolic oligomers." *Processes of Petrochemistry and Oil Refining* 21.2 (2020): 224-230.
12. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=DEaSb2sAAA&AJ&citation_for_view=DEaSb2sAAAAJ:4T0pqqG69KYC
13. Xamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "EVACUATION OF THE LEVEL OF CONFLICTS IN CONFLICT SITUATIONS BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS." *Confrencea 1.1* (2023): 23-27. <https://confrencea.org/index.php/confrenceas/article/view/372/375>
14. Khamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "MASTERY OF MANAGING PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION STUDY, GENERALIZATION AND DISSEMINATION OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 1217-1222. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/4627/4322>
15. Khamidovna M. I. CAUSES OF FAMILY CONFLICTS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 12. – C. 870-872. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3156/2907>

16. Khamidovna, M. I. (2022). The influence of older people on the formation of the spiritual environment in Uzbek families. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(10), 360-364.

https://api.scienceweb.uz/storage/publication_files/3062/8164/641d74df6fdbcb98d0bcdbf0b0d1%84d0b0d0ba%1%82d0be%1%80_7_4_d0a0d0b0d0b2%1%88d0b0d0bd%0%b6%0%be%0%bd_2_%d2%9b%0%b8%1%80%2%9b%0%b8%0%bb%0%b3%0%b0%0%bd.pdf